

Pathophysiology of the acute clinical effects of child malnutrition

Fisiopatología de los efectos clínicos agudos de la desnutrición infantil

234

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Abstract

Malnutrition imposes a significant burden of disease worldwide, particularly in children aged under 5 years.

It is intuitive to assume that a lack of energy leads to the deterioration of all physiologic functions: The lack of a proper immune response, the disruption of cardiac, renal, and pulmonary activity, and a perpetuating cycle of intestinal malabsorption are typically the chief pathophysiological components of malnutrition. Ranging from hormonal dysregulation to immune impairment, malnutrition represents a complex problem at the molecular level as well. An increased risk of infections, arrhythmias, respiratory failure, and neurological disorders are just some of the many

risks attributable to malnutrition. While the treatment options are limited to caloric and macronutrient restitution, this must be done carefully to avoid potentially fatal outcomes. The evolution of malnourished patients requires monitoring of several parameters like fluids, electrolytes, and several hormones to ensure satisfactory outcomes. Despite current knowledge of the metabolic adaptations in malnutrition, there are still a lot of unanswered questions. Further research is needed to provide better insight into the management of these conditions outside of conventional protocols.

Keywords: Child malnutrition, pathophysiology, energy metabolism, malnourishment, wasting.

La desnutrición impone una carga significativa de morbilidad en todo el mundo, particularmente en niños menores de 5 años. Es intuitivo suponer que la falta de energía conduce al deterioro de todas las funciones fisiológicas: la falta de una respuesta inmune adecuada, la alteración de la actividad cardíaca, renal y pulmonar y un ciclo perpetuado de malabsorción intestinal suelen ser las principales causas fisiopatológicas. Componentes de la desnutrición. La desnutrición, que abarca desde la desregulación hormonal hasta el deterioro inmunológico, también representa un problema complejo a nivel molecular. Un mayor riesgo de infecciones, arritmias, insuficiencia respiratoria y trastornos neurológicos son sólo algunos de los muchos riesgos atribuibles a la desnutrición. Si bien las opciones de tratamiento se limitan a la restitución de calorías y macronutrientes, esto debe hacerse con cuidado para evitar resultados potencialmente fatales. La evolución de los pacientes desnutridos requiere el seguimiento de varios parámetros como lípidos, electrolitos y varias hormonas para asegurar resultados satisfactorios. A pesar del conocimiento actual sobre las adaptaciones metabólicas en la desnutrición, todavía quedan muchas preguntas sin respuesta. Se necesitan más investigaciones para proporcionar una mejor comprensión del manejo de estas afecciones fuera de los protocolos convencionales.

Palabras clave: Desnutrición infantil, fisiopatología, metabolismo energético, desnutrición, emaciación.

Malnutrition is defined by the World Health Organization (WHO) as an imbalance in nutrition, including either deficit or excess¹. Child malnutrition has scaled to pandemic levels in the last few decades, making a significant impact on public health. Although access to food and resources is achieved effortlessly in developed countries, food deprivation remains a central problem in the developing world. Thus, a public health problem, child malnutrition encompasses both undernourished and obese children worldwide^{2,3}. In light of the above problem, several institutions and policies have risen to tackle this issue from several perspectives; and yet, child malnutrition continues to steadily rise³.

The prevalence of child obesity and undernourishment tends to vary according to the region. Nevertheless, globally, the United Nations Children's Fund (UNICEF) reported in 2019 that 144 million children under 5 years of age suffered from stunting (low height for age), 47 million were wasted (low weight for height) and 39.3 million were overweight⁴. Although these absolute numbers give a good perspective on the extent of the problem, local data reported in relative variables provides a better insight. For instance, the prevalence of stunting in Iran is nearly 20%⁵. Along these lines, 23.5% of all children in North African countries suffer from stunting, and nearly 13% are classified as underweight. Although some countries have significantly lower figures, the gravity of the situation remains evident⁶.

Undernutrition accounts for 45% of the mortality in children under 5 years of age, whether directly or indirectly⁷. However, the background of malnutrition regarding children's health goes beyond macronutrient deficits or excesses. Malnutrition creates an environment for abnormal growth, macronutrient metabolism, inflammatory responses, and impaired immunity, rendering patients prone to complications. Similarly, several hormones like insulin, thyroid hormone, growth hormone, and cortisol play a fundamental role in the pathophysiology of this condition⁸. Understanding the mechanisms related to malnutrition and its complications can provide useful tools for decision-making

and the therapeutic approach of these patients. The aim of this review is to review the pathophysiologic mechanisms of malnutrition, specifically undernourishment, to understand the associated complications like immune impairment, cardiac failure, and respiratory failure.

Acute clinical effects in malnutrition: what do we know?

Undernourishment can be molecularly defined as the absence or deficiency of nutrients brought on by an insufficient protein or energy intake. The imbalance created between the nutrient requirement and intake results in a cumulative deficit of energy, protein, and micronutrients that will impair most physiologic functions like growth and normal development⁹. Strictly speaking, acute malnutrition occurs due to insufficient nutrient intake; however, this condition is frequently presented in patients with chronic diseases that impair nutrient absorption or increase their rate of expenditure. For instance, cystic fibrosis, chronic kidney failure, childhood cancers, congenital heart disease, and neuromuscular diseases are some of the conditions that can lead to acute malnutrition⁸. Only the mechanisms related to nutrient restriction will be covered in this review.

Malnutrition itself does not have a singular form of presentation, although certain key characteristics are very consistent. Most children with malnutrition will have restricted growth and cognitive developmental issues to a certain degree¹⁰. Moreover, these patients tend to have an increased risk of infections, and indeed a large portion are initially treated for respiratory, urinary, or enteral infections. Beyond these conditions, these patients also have impaired cardiac and respiratory function, so they may present with hypotension or respiratory distress¹¹. The molecular aspects of the cardiac, respiratory, and immunological impairments will be summarized.

Insufficient energy intake triggers physiological adaptations to overcome the negative energetic balance. The most well-conserved mechanism of adaptation is decreasing the overall energy expenditure by reducing the basal metabolic rate (BMR). However, the BMR is actually increased during the first few days of starvation because of increased catecholamine levels in response to decreasing blood glucose concentrations¹². As fasting time progresses, the BMR decreases

because of lower free triiodothyronine (T3) and catecholamine levels, resulting in lower gluconeogenesis and thermogenesis rates¹³. In general, the objective of these adaptive mechanisms is to maintain a stable glucose supply to the brain and minimize the loss of lean tissue.

Loss of metabolically active tissue partly explains the adaptative mechanism during energy deprivation, but there is also evidence that the efficiency of energy metabolism increases, leading to decreased energy expenditure per unit cell mass^{14,15}. Nonetheless, despite the quantitative evidence of the latter, no corresponding molecular mechanism has been identified. It has been suggested that mitochondrial proton leakage may be reduced; this would maintain a higher gradient of protons and thus facilitate greater efficiency for ATP synthesis¹⁶. Alternatively, there may be a reduction in protein turnover and the activity of sodium/potassium ATPase, which are the processes that account for the majority of basal energy expenditure^{17,18}.

At any rate, inadequate energy intake in children will result in growth restriction so that protein and energy can be used for maintenance of the existing tissue. When the energy deficit is severe enough, it will result in the loss of body tissue, both fat and lean, to provide substrates to maintain other remaining cells. The representation of the above is the tendency to lower weight-for-height parameters, classified as wasting¹⁹⁻²¹.

In this scenario, the body needs to redistribute its resources to maintain the function of organs like the brain, heart, and kidneys; this adaptation occurs in a stepwise process. Most tissues utilize glucose as their preferred metabolic substrate in the postprandial period and then progressively switch to the use of fatty acids^{22,23}. However, the brain has an obligatory requirement for glucose, as do red blood cells, the skin, and the kidney medulla^{24,25}. As a result, glucose concentrations must be kept within acceptable ranges through the breakdown of glycogen that is stored in the liver, which is limited. After glycogen stores are depleted, glucose must be produced entirely by gluconeogenesis and the recycling of amino acids, primarily from muscle protein. As fasting continues, the liver also tends to produce ketone bodies to decrease the amount of glucose required by the brain, going from 80 grams of glucose a day to 35 grams per day in long-term starvation; however, this is just a temporary solution²⁶.

Interestingly, other types of muscle tissue may also participate at this stage. In fasting rats, the smooth muscle of the gut appears to break down more rapidly than the skeletal muscle during the initial stages of starvation²⁷. The latter obviously has implications for the functional aspects of the gut and the maintenance of the gut barrier, resulting in bacterial translocation, disruption of the microbiota, inflammation^{28,29}. Smooth muscle soon lacks the ability to provide enough amino acids for gluconeogenesis, so skeletal muscle quickly becomes the main source of amino acids. Studies appear to show that all skeletal muscles are affected equally, with a predisposition for type II fibers instead of type I³⁰.

Likewise, a lack of resources to maintain normal enteral tissue exchange results in villous atrophy with loss of disaccharidases, crypt hypoplasia, and altered intestinal permeability, resulting in malabsorption and thus perpetuating a vicious cycle¹⁰. Furthermore, pancreatic atrophy has been reported in undernourished patients, worsening the overall absorption of fatty acids³¹. Similarly, it has been reported that decreased production of albumin and binding proteins results in altered drug metabolism, making the selection of drugs even harder in these cases³².

Muscle function tends to progressively worsen as starvation continues, resulting in increased fatigability and decreased muscle strength. Muscle impairment is macroscopically expressed as limited mobility; however, the most serious consequence of the above is the loss of respiratory muscle, leading to an impaired ability to cough and thus increasing the susceptibility to respiratory infections, not to mention the alterations of the respiration itself³³. On the other hand, cardiac myofibrils are also thinned during protein turnover, resulting in impaired contractility. The above-mentioned results in decreased cardiac output, which is proportionate to the weight loss. The combination of decreased inotropism, chronotropism, and electrolyte imbalances predisposes to arrhythmias and other cardiac complications^{34,35}.

The immune system is also affected. Cellular immunity is severely compromised due to atrophy of the thymus, lymph nodes, and tonsils. Likewise, there is reduced differentiation of lymphocytes, impaired hypersensitivity responses, delayed phagocytosis, loss of opsonization, and reduced production of secretory immunoglobulin A³⁶⁻³⁸. Consequently,

patients' susceptibility to invasive infections of any source is greatly increased, as are their chances of developing sepsis.

The lack of a proper immune response, the deteriorating cardiac, renal, and pulmonary functions, and the perpetuating cycle of intestinal malabsorption are typically the chief pathophysiological components of malnutrition. Intuitively, the answer to these problems could be to provide a positive balance of energy and macronutrients. Nonetheless, the refeeding syndrome (RFS) is a potentially fatal condition that commonly occurs in undernourished patients exposed to rapid changes in fluid and electrolyte balance, leading to cardiac arrhythmias or cardiac and respiratory failure. Other manifestations of the RFS are acute hepatic steatosis, hematological abnormalities, acute thiamine deficiency, delirium, and centropontine myelinolysis³⁹.

In consequence, malnutrition demands careful management in order to avoid RFS. Zeki et al.⁴⁰ showed that the occurrence of refeeding hypophosphatemia is higher in orally fed patients in contrast to parenteral feeding. It was concluded that enteral feeding resulted in greater insulin secretion due to the incretin effect. Other authors have suggested using biochemical parameters to predict the likelihood of RFS. For instance, the refeeding index, a score generated from baseline insulin-like growth factor (IGF-1) and leptin, was proposed as a biochemical score to predict the risk of RFS. Similarly, a study in 2015 demonstrated that measuring IGF-1 alone had high sensitivity and specificity for identifying patients at high risk of refeeding hypophosphatemia^{41,42}.

Malnutrition imposes a significant burden of disease, particularly in children aged under 5 years, accounting directly or indirectly for almost half the mortality. It is intuitive to assume that a lack of energy will slowly result in the collapse of physiologic functions. Ranging from hormonal dysregulation to immune impairment, malnutrition represents a complex problem at the molecular level as well. An increased risk of infections, arrhythmias, respiratory failure, and neurological disorders are just some of the problems attributable to malnutrition. While the treatment options are limited to caloric and macronutrient restitution, this must be done carefully to avoid potentially fatal outcomes. The evolution of malnourished patients requires monitoring of several parameters like fluids, electrolytes, and several hormones to ensure satisfactory outcomes. Despite current knowledge of the metabolic adaptations in malnutrition, there are still a lot of unanswered questions. Further research is needed to provide better insight into the management of these conditions outside of conventional protocols.

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